

DOI:

ABSTRACT

Today shortly after many escalations, conflict mediation across clients, non-services teams spanning few hours. I wanted to put across a brief note of what I've read, learnt, understood about Service Delivery. It is the tip (an article) of an iceberg (research project). One can refer it and acknowledge the mindset, discipline of Service delivery as an individual, probably a self reminder by me.

Still I am learning everyday as the ocean of knowledge is vast enough but want to conclude and share experiences I have gained, knowledge I have earned, challenges I have faced and problems I have solved in my 16 years of experience. I am describing all these by taking my career as an age of a man. A 16 year old teenager (My Career), always curious to know and learn, intrigued by the way things have been and are in Life called Services Delivery (i.e. Every Project, Operation, Upgrade, Consulting Assignment, Merger and Acquisitions, Migration, Transition ++ and even a Quarterly Biz Report for that matter).

It reached it's adolescence (Mid-management level, 8 yrs) when Service Delivery Framework (SDF) was used interchangeably with the term Service Delivery Platform (SDP) which are set of technology components that provide capabilities. SDF governed and guided the use of SDP capabilities as such.

KEYWORDS:

INTRODUCTION

SERVICE DELIVERY FRAMEWORKS (SDFs):

Now like every normal teenager, it has had it's share of crush, infatuations and breakups (read/heard--proposed/used--dissatisfied/changed) with varied categories of such SDFs:

A. Strategic Framework: It is an inclusive portrait of the organisations strategy. It clarifies how to achieve the best outcome by individual efforts and team projects. It includes the meaningful target measures and a sequence of activities that help focus on the key efforts that implement the strategy.

B. Tactical Framework: A tactic is a conceptual action implemented as one or more specific tasks. This kind of service delivery framework necessitates a focused approach converging to a specific resolution and/ or accomplishment. These are mostly used as a customized way out to address a unique situation of a requirement.

C. Operational Framework: It is a guide to a policies, goals, standards, procedures and training of a company. A company does business and promotes a corporate culture and identity by the ways of this frame work.

Now fast forwarding the story to contained state-of-mind for a middle-aged person (My Career). I believe that-Services are a process of transition/transformation; from inception/ideation to delivery rather than a mere product/offering.

Services are; therefore; heterogeneous fundamentally. A Service provider and Customer need to create the service values that meet, bind the respective needs of the customer and the capability of service provider.

ASPECTS FOR SERVICE

This aspect of co-creation for service values is enabled in modern times by-

- Digitization
- Social media
- Communication technology
- Big data technologies and analytics
- Collaborative methods and tools (read as integration of resources and information)

CORE ELEMENTS OF SERVICE:

Irrespective of nature and industry/domain of service, the core elements to it are:

- Resource (needed for delivery)
- Provider (who will deliver)
- Customer (to be delivered to)
- Time (till delivery completes)
- Benefits (post delivery)

PHASES OF A SERVICE LIFE- CYCLE

Similarly crux, of various service life-cycle approaches can be phased as

- Learn (conceive the concept by capturing dynamics of demand against which we need to supply services)
- Develop (physical/soft/hybrid resources interact to be leveraged in order to facilitate the outcome intended)
- Perform (service provisioned, integrated to adapt with end user environment, encounters noted)
- Improve (trends, service encounters of customer base influence the provider's quantum of improvement; 0 to 360 degree; as applicable)

ATTRIBUTES OF SERVICE:

All service life-cycles have an inherent set of following attributes mandated

- Innovation (by transformation of resources for competition, process of delivering and improving)
- Performance (by monitoring in real-time against ability of outcome/delivery to meet needs of end user)
- Value Creation (from conceptualization, through development, to delivery)
- Value Proposition (appropriately measured, monitored, and realized in the process of service provision)

Continuing where I left in last synopsis; now I will share the modus-operandi that I devised to survive the expectations as Service Delivery Enabler/Auditor/Facilitator/Conductor.

Ironically, delivery is confiscated by the realms of ESAT to ensure Time, Scope, Quality, CSAT thus BizSAT (just as projects..a type of Service Delivery). Accentuating the needs of successful delivery are unique to factors and catalysts of An Industry yet eventually it's the broad categorizations of realms as in preceding sentence.

What matter's most is that one should form basis of "*ability to deliver*" and map it with what's "*needed to be delivered*". In almost all noticeable debacles there is an inherent mismatch of these two. I am trying to outline below the inherent ingredients which must be combined to define the 'Duo'; respectively.

ABILITY TO DELIVER

1. Right Resources identified and available (with fallback plan)
2. Agreed and Approved Scope + Methodology across stakeholders
3. Validation/ Checkpoints for Progress and Quality
4. Delegation to right people with due accountability and authority
5. Change/Correction Management
6. Buffers (practical) to absorb the deviations of time/cost/scope and risks inherent
7. Periodic Updates/Patches/Upgrade
8. Handover Requisites (if applicable)

9. Knowledge-base (Takeaways/Vendor as well as Operations-Manual/Client) and
10. Confirmation as well as Acceptance of Completion by Client.

NEEDED TO BE DELIVERED

1. The Sought + Scoped Outcome and Change/Upgrade/ Capability endowed by essence of outcome
2. Characteristic absorption of delivered service/product in active delivery/production environment
3. Scalability and Migration switches (identifiers, processing-mechanism, indicators of the failure/completion/compliance)
4. Lifespan and justification of the Demand equated with Supply/Delivery of Service.

Looking at the constituents of the "Ability to Deliver" and what's "Needed to be Delivered" any and every Service Delivery can be improved/enhanced/optimized while retaining it's commercial viability.

I've used this non empirical relation between Ability of Service Delivery and it's Need to sustain the portfolios across BFSI, Healthcare, IT, Telecom, ITeS, FMCG, Automobile, Education and Consulting verticals for 16 years now.

I employed what has helped me to look at, imbibe, utilize in terms of reference and learning all my life..sort of Memory Maps..which are succinct and sufficient with a basic understanding.

There is this leash called SLA used by clients to not let vendors go astray on deliverables. And if they do then penalize them for the commercial hit that non-delivery has caused. Right..? More or less, this is how it has been acknowledged so far.

Primarily, any service/product/goods need to accomplish certain pre-defined outcomes and the so called SLAs are articulated to keep a tab on this delivery, limiting impact of delivery disruption.

Services are essentially a business requirement for both Vendor and Client therefore no one would like to under perform while DELIVERING it and while UTILISING it TO DELIVER further.

CONDITIONS OF DELIVERY

Now this bonsai ecosystem needs necessarily following to thrive upon the requisites of Delivery for both the entities involved--

1. The Scope: Identified and Quantified, This efficacy of delivery primarily depends upon it.
2. The Cost: Paid by client as Billed by vendor, This comprises of both CapEx and OpEx for the Delivery to take off and sustain.
3. The Value/Benefit: Added to the portfolio of client by virtue of services, It is the complimenting effect that Service has on eventual delivery by the client's business model.
4. The Degree of Restoration: TAT/Turn-around-Time directly proportional to Functional-Calibration, Mandatory to achieve quickest BAU/Biz-as-Usual status post an outage/ disruption of the agreed/scoped Service Delivery.
5. The Monitoring and Reporting: Performance Trend for Services Delivered in a given tenure, This may/may not be an extra cost for vendor depending on the level + frequency of details, parameters to be captured, reported.

RELATION BETWEEN VENDOR AND CLIENT

Now the give-n-take relations among a vendor and client are tethered by the following questions:-

1. What is to be delivered and what is being delivered
2. How it is monitored in terms of expected outcome and reported

Meeting SLA doesn't mean quality of service delivery is good.. so far SLA is used as an indemnification or simply a risk mitigating tool by the client against threat that dependency on vendor poses.

This interestingly brings us to another question pertaining to Risk Analysis of this Demand-and-Supply chain; Does the benchmark used in monitoring balances interest of both vendor and client? Let's try to shift our focus from

traditional client-vendor relation to that of a collaborative and more of a partnership among the Service Provider and Service Utiliser.

Essentially the Cost versus Benefit analysis forms basis for Risk Analysis balancing interests of provider and receiver entity.

REQUIREMENT OF SERVICE LEVERAGING ADAPTATION a.k.a. SLA: Service Level Agreement

The SERVICE LEVERAGING ADAPTATION will need both client and vendor to define their targets in a collinear fashion e.g. Revenue Share model used by VAS providers to Telecom service providers. This ensures that client attains an enhanced participation by vendor in eventual ecosystem of services to be provided.

- Vendor will gain or lose with client and therefore will have to proactively uphold accountability of delivery
- Client can allow a flexible co-existence of multiple vendors to facilitate a healthy and open competition thus ensuring enhancement as well as biz continuity
- Distinguished services will need to survive the dynamics of client's market therefore agility and scalability will be inherent to entire delivery lifecycle ahead
- Monitoring, reporting of the defined matrices will certainly be regular and therefore trend recognition and due alterations will be highlighted with active deviations along.

This is catching up with the Service Providers and Receivers as they enter next phase of business sustenance which will be enabled by IoT/Internet of Things where coexistence is not an option but necessitation due to the meshed ecosystem blurring very boundaries of Respective ownership while turning it into a state of "Together We Stand..Divided We Fall"

I will be glad to befit the same to any need of Service Delivery if sought by any of you out there; all you need to do is reach out.

I resorted to intense brevity above as this topic is enormous if the details of each bullet item only even are to be elaborated. I look forward to suggestions, comments, correction, discussions alike. Thanks in Advance..!!